

***Allá en la Patagonia*, by María Brunswig de Bamberg: A Model of Research, Editing and Rewriting of the Family Archive**

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Abstract

In the illustrated book *Allá en la Patagonia* (1995), the German Argentinian translator María Brunswig de Bamberg (Berlin, 1915–2016) recounts the adventures and daily routines of her family, German migrants in Argentina, focusing on the period from 1919 to 1929, when the parents and their five children lived in Patagonian lands. The fragmentary text becomes a dialogue among three generations of women, as the editor-translator-writer edits and comments on the old letters that her mother, Ella Hoffmann de Brunswig (1893–1990), wrote describing her journey and her life in Patagonia to her mother (María's grandmother), Emma Augusta Voss (1871–1958), who lived in Lübeck, Germany. The voice of Ella, and the comments and memories written in the present by María, are complemented by texts and photographs by Hermann Brunswig, the husband and father. The author intertwines 277 fragments chosen from these textual and photographic files, and the hybrid combination results in a fluent masterpiece of editing. This outcome is not surprising, given the professional experience of María Bamberg as a literary translator, which is another kind of writing (or rewriting) art. For 26 years, since her return to Berlin in 1963, she introduced the Latin American "Boom" to German readers, translating novels such as Carlos Fuentes' *Terra nostra*. This study analyses her 317-page chronicle and its relations with migrations and testimonial literature, as a model of the editorial possibilities of domestic, private and family archives to document meaningful stories and understand history and society from untold points of view.

Keywords

Argentina; Germany; travel; migration; literature; women

The Finding of a Book

I was at the end of a month-long research stay in Argentina within the Latin American-European project Trans.Arch (Archives in Transition), when one day in July 2023, roaming in the company of my colleague Rafa Oliver through the bibliophile paradise that is the bookstores of Corrientes Avenue in Buenos Aires, a woman on the red cover of a pocketbook caught my attention from the middle of a pile of volumes: it showed the picture of a young lady, at the beginning of the twentieth century, wearing an elegant dress and a flowery pamelita hat, seated in a cane armchair and looking at the viewer with clear, dreamy eyes. *Allá en la Patagonia* (*Over There in Patagonia*) was the title, and the subtitle, *La vida de una mujer en una tierra inhóspita* (*The Life of a Woman in an Inhospitable Land*), referred to the charming girl of the portrait who was to endure such an adventure in the remotesouth of Argentina. The author of the biography was María Brunswig de Bamberg, or María Bamberg, the eldest daughter of Ella Hoffmann de Brunswig, the protagonist in the picture.

I had travelled across Argentina and beyond, from the capital to Jujuy, and on to Salta, Tucumán, Simoca, San Ignacio Miní, Santa Fe, Paraná, Rosario, Calafate, Río

Gallegos, the Chilean Strait of Magellan, and Ushuaia, with stops in Asunción, Paraguay, and at the Itaipú Dam in Brazil. This book addressed several of the subjects that most interested me during that journey: migration, travel, geography, testimonial literature, and the use of letters, diaries, photographs, and other materials from domestic and private archives to construct meaningful narratives and to understand history and society from intimate and unexplored perspectives. I bought it for 1,000 pesos (around two euros at the time). The promising book, published in Buenos Aires by Javier Vergara Editor in 1998, was the second edition of the original version printed in 1995, with an added epilogue.

With this copy in hand I thought that I could connect it with the documents and objects that I had seen weeks before at Museo de la Inmigración, the Museum of Immigration, established at Hotel de Inmigrantes, the building by the North dock of the Buenos Aires harbour which was built in 1905 to function, until 1953, as a temporary shelter and registration centre—as Ellis Island in New York—for the immigrants coming from all over the world in the first half of the twentieth century (Universidad Nacional Tres de Febrero). Around one million people stayed at this free state hotel during that period, including tens of thousands of German citizens from Germany itself and, mainly, ethnic Germans from the Volga riverbed in Russia, who started to arrive in 1876 (Embajada “200 años”). The arrival rate increased after the German defeat in World War I and the hyperinflation crisis, with 72,054 German citizens registered officially as immigrants in Argentina from 1919 to 1932, which represented half of the more than 140,000 Germans who migrated to Latin America in those years (Gutiérrez Koester “Man schwimmt” 19-20). Nowadays, out of the 46.2 million Argentines (2022 Census), around 600,000 to one million have ancestors from Germany and another 2.5 million are descendants of Russian-Germans from the Volga, according to different estimations, which makes the people with German-speaking origins the third-largest community in Argentina (“Inmigración”).

Allá en la Patagonia also interested me because it related to the landscapes and the people that I had seen and met just a few days before in the stage of my trip to Patagonia and Tierra del Fuego, passing through Lake Argentino, the glaciers of the Andes, or the vast wastelands of the Atlantic coast, the same sceneries Ella Hoffmann, her husband Hermann, her daughter María and the rest of her family inhabited exactly one hundred years before. The most deserved homage to my dear colleague and friend Roland Spiller has triggered the opportunity—with his farewell congress *Beyond the Archive* celebrated at Goethe-Universität in Frankfurt in July 2025, and the present book with the contributions—to study the volume that I found, not by chance, two years before in that bookstore in Corrientes Avenue. Argentina, Patagonia, Germany, travels, archives, books, the literature in Spanish and, above all, people, are ingredients that I believe match very well the subject of our tribute to Professor Spiller and his own personal interests. The story of a German family who emigrated in the early 1920s to Patagonia, a very isolated place at the end of the world, to earn a living like so many others do today everywhere, is a topic that not only links Germany with Argentina, Europe with America, but also reminds us of the universal nature of migrations, always a crucial political issue.

Moreover, *Allá en la Patagonia*, as we’ll see, is—for researchers, journalists, writers, editors, readers—a model of the editorial possibilities of family archives, those hidden and humble treasures. María Bamberg’s work may inspire and encourage writers, scholars, archivists, artists, documentary filmmakers and others to study something we all have at hand, because, as I tell my Journalism students, family archives—

documents of all kinds from our parents, grandparents, great-grandparents, and *plus ultra*—are what we need to start an interesting research.

Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. The cover of *Allá en la Patagonia* (1998) with the picture of Ella Hoffmann de Brunswig in 1912, and a portrait of Hermann Brunswig in 1914, included in the book.

The Editor-Writer-Translator

Born in Berlin, María Brunswig de Bamberg (1915–2016), or María Bamberg as she signed other works, was seven years old when on January 6, 1923, she embarked on the ship *Vigo* in Hamburg with her mother, Ella Hoffmann de Brunswig (1893–1990), her two younger twin sisters, Irene (Ija or Iya, 1917) and Ana-Luisa (Asse, 1917–1997), and a woman who worked for the family as a cook and nurse, Berta Freytag (?–1930?), with the mission of reuniting in Argentina with her father, Hermann Brunswig (1883–1971), a former captain in the German Navy. After his country's defeat in World War I and while fighting as a militia commander against the Spartacist Uprising of 1919 during the Weimar Republic, Hermann accepted the suggestion of his eldest brother, Peter, a bank officer at Banco Trasatlántico Alemán in Santiago de Chile, to find a way out of the German economic collapse by emigrating to America. Hermann travelled alone from Rotterdam to Buenos Aires in October 1919 on the steamer *Frisia*, and by 1923 he was working as the manager of a German sheep farm in Patagonia, an *estancia* or *hacienda* of 250 square kilometres and 10,000 sheep, by Lake Ghío. The family reunited in 1923 in Patagonia and grew there with the birth of two sons: Hermann Lucas (Hermancito, 1925) and Bernardo (Bernd, 1927).

Ella Hoffmann returned temporarily to Germany with her children in 1929, and María, the eldest, stayed there to study secondary school. In 1934, after the ascent to power of the Nazi regime under Adolf Hitler, María returned to Argentina, not for political reasons but to help her mother, who had come back to Patagonia, to educate the younger brothers. It was only then, in her new stay in Argentina, that she learned Spanish, because during the first period her mother had taken care of the children in an isolated atmosphere, with a purely German culture, and had prevented them from learning the language of the natives, workers of a lower class. The adult María became a professor of German and English at Universidad Nacional de Córdoba, and married a gynaecologist, another German émigré, Paul Hans Bamberg, a Jew from Berlin who in 1938 had escaped from Nazi persecution. The couple settled in San Rafael, in Mendoza province, had four children and, following the wishes of her husband, moved back to Berlin in 1963. María's parents, sisters and brothers remained in Argentina.

In her new phase in Germany, María Bamberg started to read in depth, for the first time, Latin American literature and became a highly skilled literary translator from Spanish to German of some of the most important masters of the “Boom”, with the Mexican Carlos Fuentes—with whom she developed a close relationship for 13 years—as her main writer. She translated Fuentes' novels such as *Terra nostra*, *Cristóbal Nonato*, and *La cabeza de la hidra*. In the list of books that she introduced to German readers during her 26 years as a “housewife translator” appear titles such as *Sor Juana Inés de la Cruz o las trampas de la fe*, by the Mexican Octavio Paz, or *El camino de El Dorado*, by the Venezuelan Arturo Uslar Pietri. She taught translation and Latin American studies at the Free University of Berlin, acted as a cultural mediator between Latin

America and Germany in lectures, colloquia and book presentations, and helped Chilean refugees after Pinochet's military coup of 1973. She was awarded the Federal Cross of Merit by the Federal Republic of Germany. María died on 4 June 2016 in Berlin, the same city where she was born one hundred and a half years earlier, on 10 December 1915.

The information about the author comes from these sources: her mentioned book *Allá en la Patagonia* and the biographical note, under her picture, in the flap of the first edition; an interview in August 2002 in Berlin with the researcher Jennifer M. Valko (published in 2022); her memoirs, "Memories of two worlds", published in 2004 in Germany (*Zwischen Argentinien und Deutschland: Erinnerungen in zwei Welten*) and in 2011 in Argentina (*Memorias de dos mundos*); a review of this autobiography published by her friend Esther Andradi in the Mexican magazine *La Jornada Semanal* (19 February 2012), and two obituaries after her death: one by her German editor at Tranvía publishing house Walter Frey (July 2016), and other by journalist Tatjana Wulfert in the newspaper *Der Tagesspiegel* (25 November 2016).

Fig. 3. María Bamberg, daughter of Ella and Hermann, in the 1995 Argentinian edition of her book *Allá en la Patagonia*.

To Edit Is to Create: The Materials and the Reconstruction

In *Allá en la Patagonia*, María Brunswig de Bamberg recounts the adventures and daily routines of her family, German migrants in Argentina, focusing on the period from 1919 to 1929, when they lived in Patagonian provinces. The fragmentary text becomes a dialogue among three generations of women, as the editor-translator-writer, María, edits and comments on old letters describing her journey and her life in Patagonia that her mother, Ella, wrote and sent to her own mother (María's grandmother), Emma Augusta Voss (1871–1958), called familiarly Mutt or Mutti, who was living in Lübeck, Germany. The letters and other later writings of Ella and the comments and memories in the present written by María, the daughter and editor, are complemented with other texts by the man of the family, Hermann Brunswig, Ella's husband and María's father: articles that he published in 1969 in *Argentinisches Tageblatt*, the Buenos Aires newspaper for the German community in Argentina; a conference in the Club Alemán given in the 1950s; notes, and some letters he wrote to his mother-in-law. Hermann also took, developed and printed the pictures of their experiences in Patagonia that illustrate the book.

María intertwines numerous fragments chosen from that textual and photographic family archive, with her added comments. We may count: From Ella, 74 letters to her mother, two letters to her stepfather, ten fragments of her memoirs, and one oral testimony to her daughter María; by Hermann, two newspaper articles, one conference, nine letters and notes to his mother-in-law, one telegram, one chronicle; by María, 35 commentaries to the edition and seven footnotes, plus the introduction, a narration from her youth and the epilogue; two letters between two friends of the family, the Patagonian landowners Max Wlotzel (Uncle Max) and Lucas Bridges; one letter from Peter to his brother Hermann; two maps; one family tree; 62 black and white pictures by Hermann, and two studio portraits, with their corresponding (all but one) 63 captions written by María. In total at least 277 pieces were used; another list would be that of the elements that were discarded.

The hybrid combination of these materials, that could produce a chaotic pastiche, results, on the contrary, in an accomplished masterpiece of editing craft arranged in chronological order. This outcome is not surprising when we consider the professional experience of María Bamberg as a literary translator, which is another kind of writing (or rewriting) art. She is an example of the editor becoming an author herself. The editor, the person who gathers, compiles and edits the materials, ultimately becomes a first-rate writer, because whoever chooses the texts that go in and the structure, is truly building the narrative. In this case, from gluing little fragments, family pieces that we all have lying around at home, often overlooked. Her carefully edited 317-page book shows us how to bring order to the jumble on the desk. That's where the editor's role comes in. Editing is about compiling and creating; we don't just accumulate documents, we give them meaning by selecting and discarding them.

This edition was a demanding endeavour, as the author stated in the opening page. But if someone were to attempt the same task now, in the second quarter of the 21st century, it would probably be a much more complicated, even endless task, to filter and edit such a family chronicle. In the 1920s, letters were handwritten and it took weeks, or even months, to be delivered, making them scarcer and easier to collect. But these days, instead of those handwritten letters, we instantly communicate through thousands upon thousands of WhatsApp messages, photos, videos, emoticons, and voice recordings. That's why we might need artificial intelligence (AI) tools to help us process oceans of information when editing massive files.

Fig. 4. María (left), with her mother Ella and her twin sisters Asse and Iya, in Lago Posadas in 1923, in a picture of *Allá en la Patagonia* taken by her father, Hermann.

After a page of acknowledgements, and the index, the book starts with a prologue with the first letter that Ella wrote to her mother, Mutti, as she waited aboard the *Vigo* in Hamburg for the departure to Buenos Aires. From the beginning, the literary quality of Ella's epistolary narrative becomes evident:

Here's your little Ella, sitting in the cabin—the steamer doesn't sail for another hour—who can send you one last greeting, which the pilot will dispatch tonight from Cuxhaven.

So from now on: courage and strength for whatever comes! Fate won't crush us, not at all! I haven't opened your letters yet. I'm saving them for later, when we're on the high seas. Right now, there's a lot of noise on board, and one feels very soft, very full of mixed emotions. But I'm already wearing your ring, Mutt, and its sparkle tells me of all your love, of the good wishes and greetings your heart sends me. It will be a good companion, in good times and bad. When I touch it, I feel in my hand that you are with me, even though seas and lands separate us. You will always be who you were, and your little Ella will be able to rest near you, always.

Thank you, Mutt, a thousand thanks.

Ella. (Brunswig de Bamberg 11)¹

The prologue is completed with the first comment, in italics, by the editor-writer María, who, more than seven decades later, adds context, explaining that the group of women arrived in Buenos Aires on 3 February 1923, after a month of sailing, and that, after two

¹ All quotations are taken from the original Spanish text of the 1998 Argentinian edition. The English translations are from Google Translate and were subsequently revised by the author for accuracy and clarity.

days of rest, they departed again aboard a coastal steamer to San Julián, south along the Atlantic Patagonian coast. From there, they travel for three days by motorcar through rough, wild paths until reaching the *estancia* by Lake Ghío, their residence, where Hermann was waiting for them.

Individual full portraits of her mother and her father in 1912 and 1914 follow, before and Introduction by María to explain the origins of both well-to-do middle class families, a useful genealogical tree, and an independent chapter with the “History of this book”, where she explains the editorial steps taken and the materials chosen to construct the volume.

Hermann Brunswig, following a suggestion of Mutti’s second husband, the retired general Franz Sydow, and with his assistance, made a selection of the letters that Ella sent to her mother from Argentina to Germany from 1919 until 1958, when the recipient died. Hermann typewrote the selected letters with the idea of publishing a book. María doesn’t explain how her father, who never came back to his native country, received a copy of the letters from Germany. The book was not published, but, instead, Hermann presented the epistolary chronicle that he had edited in a single copy to her wife Ella for a birthday, including his pictures of the Patagonian years. Later on, Ella, in 1977, wrote a 40-page notebook, in German, with her memoirs of that period, titled *Unser Anfang in Südamerika* (*Our beginning in South America*), also called *Recuerdos de la Patagonia* (*Memories of Patagonia*), and gave a copy to each of her five children. That notebook didn’t include her old letters collected by her husband, so it was a new story of the same events portrayed in the epistolary dialogue with her mother half a century earlier. In this new narration as an old woman she included aspects that she hadn’t mentioned in the letters of her youth to avoid worrying Mutti.

At that point, her daughter María, as she explains (Brunswig de Bamberg 18–20), decided to intervene for the first time as an editor of the family saga, to spread the story among other relatives, and combined the two texts: Ella’s letters to her mother collected by Hermann, and Ella’s notebook of 1977. The product was a book, printed in German in Berlin in 1979, with two editions: a first of 18 copies and a second of 500 plus 300 copies, paid for by Ella (the first batch) and María (the rest). It was titled *Unsere ersten Jahre: Briefe aus Patagonien von Ella Brunswig* (*Our Early Years: Letters from Patagonia, by Ella Brunswig*), and carried as editors the names of María Bamberg and Ella Brunswig.

When María and her husband Peter, she continues, were living in Berlin, they moved in 1983 to the house of her aunt Wera, younger sister of Ella, and Wera gave her a package with Ella’s original letters to Mutti, the mother, from 1923 to her death in 1958. Then María, the family editor, could access and read in its integrity the letters that her father, Hermann, had used to prepare his old selection. She discovered that Hermann and the grandfather Sydow (Mutti’s second husband) had suppressed in their previous selection many expressions of “depression and anguish in the face of an uncertain future, making her appear like a bronze rock, never assailed by doubts or discouragements”.

In the third version of the story, in 1995, María adds that she is correcting those suppressions to give a more accurate and complete image of her mother. Nevertheless, the editor clarifies that she has also suppressed passages of the letters, not reproducing them in full, to prevent them from becoming too long. “Even so, I think Ella seems more authentic to us now”, she considers. María also uses some letters of Hermann to his mother-in-law, which were in the same pack of letters that her aunt Wera gave her.

María tells that she took the decision to prepare this last extended version of the story when she travelled back to Patagonia in February 1992, after her last visit in 1959,

and went from Río Gallegos to Calafate and Lago Argentino, feeling again the strong wind of her childhood when she landed in San Julián. It was on this last occasion that she thought of writing and including her own impressions, moving between German and Spanish. The result was the beautifully written and edited *Allá en la Patagonia*, that she finished (as her signature at the end of this chapter indicates) in Buenos Aires in March 1995. The book was published first in Spanish in 1995, in Buenos Aires. For this edition María received an important help: Anita Dürnhöfer de Meyer, from Sierra de la Ventana, province of Buenos Aires, translated to Spanish the first German edition of the story (of 1979), and Esther Andradi reviewed the first version of the Spanish manuscript written by María, as she mentions in her acknowledgements. The book sold well in the biographical field. In her second Argentinian edition of *Allá en la Patagonia*, in 1998, María included an epilogue, “Answer to a question”, to inform readers about the destiny of the protagonists of the family after the Patagonian adventure.

The German edition of the book appeared in 1998 in Hamburg: *Ella und der Gringo mit den großen Füßen: Eine deutsche Familiengeschichte in Patagonien* (“Ella and the gringo with big feet. A German family story in Patagonia”).

Complementing the editorial story of the book, there’s a “Chronology of the travels” of the family in Patagonia illustrated with a map (21–23). These materials prepare us to better understand the core of the narration which follows with Ella’s letters—the main part—and memories, María’s remarks, and Hermann’s texts and photos. The story is divided in two parts, centred in the two *estancias* where they lived: “La casa del Ghío” (1919–1924), in Santa Cruz province, chapters 1–13, and “Estancia Chacayal: 1925–1929”, in Neuquén province, chapters 14–19. The narration recalls first the experiences of Hermann in the three and a half years that he lived alone, then the arrival of the family, their daily life in the sheep farms, and their travels around Patagonia and to their second destination, via Chile.

Fig. 5. Workers Lindolfo Bello and Ramón Agüera attend the shearing at the sheep wool producing farm where Hermann Brunswig was the manager. He took the picture, which illustrates *Allá en la Patagonia*.

Working in a New World

Several genres come together in this edited chronicle, which is an autobiographical testimony “that straddles the line between epistolary novel, diary, and travelogue” (Gutiérrez Koester, “Cartas” 276; my trans.). There are many layers of meaning, too: the life of a foreign woman in an isolated place; German migration to America, particularly to Argentina and Patagonia, and its different social classes—this family belonging to the upper-middle level of skilled workers—; the cultural and natural clash and contrast between the *civilized* Europe and the Patagonian wilderness, and the processes of narration and edition themselves, which are on the basis of the construction of this story. The preservation of her German cultural identity, her struggle to adapt to the new world and circumstances, and also the surprise and wonder in the face of this strange reality (from the colossal eggs of *ñandú* devoured by her children, to the customs of local *ovejeros*, sheep herders of gaucho or indigenous origin), are the main topics behind Ella’s descriptions.

Ella and the children arrived in Patagonia in the aftermath of the killings of labourers following the mass strikes and revolts of 1920–1921. The workers, organized

by anarchists and union leaders, protested on the farms against their low salaries and miserable living conditions, with dirty and overcrowded rooms for dozens of men, poor food and lack of hygiene. Hermann was involved in the revolt when working as a member of the managing team at Estancia La Anita, near Calafate, in Santa Cruz province, south of Lake Argentino. But he was not one of the protesters who took hold of the farm, but one of the hostages. He explained decades later, in a conference at Club Alemán and an article in *Argentinisches Tageblatt*, quoted by his daughter María (30–32), how he managed to escape by wearing his old German military medals and introducing himself to the leaders of the rebellion as a kind of diplomat sent by the German government to learn the wool trade in Patagonia. He argued that it would be better for them to release him to avoid a conflict with the German authorities. They accepted, and he wrote, in good Spanish (he and his wife Ella, who had not yet arrived, had taken Spanish classes in Germany before moving, as María recounted in 2002), a *laissez-passer* that the self-proclaimed president of Southern-Patagonia signed on 11 January 1921.

Tragic, on the other hand, was the destiny of many of those labourers who had erupted against injustice in La Anita and other *estancias*. The landowners called for the intervention of the Argentine Army, which, under the command of General Héctor Varela, arrived and violently repressed the uprising for labour rights. Around 1,500 workers and union leaders were arrested, shot dead by firing squads and thrown into the mass graves they had been forced to dig, many of them at La Anita, as historian Osvaldo Bayer (surname of German origin, too) documented in his masterpiece *La Patagonia rebelde*. Luis Milton Ibarra Philemón, chronicler of Calafate, a friend and contributor of Osvaldo Bayer, took me in his car one sunset in July 2023 to Estancia La Anita and its surroundings to show me the site of the mass killing and the memorial created by the Commission for the Memory of the Patagonian Strikes of 1921.

One of the signs remembering the events cited the case of two German labourers who were executed for participating in the strike. Juan Faure, former soldier of the 19 Cavalry Regiment, told Bayer, as quoted in the sign: “No. We had refused to dig the graves. We burned them with gasoline. Yes, I did the shooting, I remember, there were eight strikers, among them a German who wasn’t killed by the first shot, who pointed to a button on his vest and said: ‘Aim here’. Before that, he had shaken hands with another German to say goodbye”. Hermann Brunswig recalls the slaughter in the article quoted in her daughter’s book:

On the second day, I ran into Colonel Héctor Varela and his superior officer, Commander Adalid, who, at the head of their troops, were “scoping” the countryside by car. In 1921, Varela quelled the revolt that had reignited, having the ringleaders executed in cold blood, their bodies falling into the pits they themselves had dug. A year later, Varela was shot dead in Buenos Aires, in the middle of the street, by one of the survivors, who was then stabbed to death by Varela’s orderly. (Brunswig de Bamberg 32)

Fig. 6. Estancia La Anita, where Hermann worked in 1920–1921, site of the main massacre of workers.

Fig. 7. Luis Milton Ibarra Philemón, near La Anita, at the memorial for the victims.

Fig. 8. View of Lago Argentino and the Andes, by the road from Calafate to La Anita.

The amazement at the sight of the wild, wide, so different landscape of Patagonia is enthusiastically expressed when Ella, in the first, long letter to her mother once she arrives to her destination, describes the three-day trip by car from the coast of San Julián to the *hacienda* in the footsteps of the Andes where her husband was waiting for them. Ella feels, in wonder, that they are in another time and world, and she likes it very much:

These three days in the car have been the highlight of our trip so far. I don't understand how anyone could find this landscape boring. Only at sea have I seen such grandeur, vastness, and power! I have rarely been as impressed as I am by this prehistoric land. It seems that we, tiny human beings, have no place here. If a dinosaur had suddenly appeared, it wouldn't have surprised us at all; we would have accepted it as something native. The very enormous carts that traverse this land belong here, while our little car seemed like an affront. (Brunswig de Bamberg 40)

After settling into the isolated house on Lake Ghío, the letters focus on telling her adaptation and domestic routines, thus providing valuable sociological information about the relationship with the native workers and the role of women, an intrepid version of the housewife, in these rural settlements. In addition to her domestic chores, she assists pregnant women as a midwife trained in Germany. Ella is overworked, as she explains to her mother when describing the *gift* Hermann gave her:

One of the most difficult aspects is the laundry: there's no kettle or tub, so I have to manage as best I can. When we arrived, I was faced with a pile of Hermann's dirty clothes, which had accumulated over months, just waiting for me. We hadn't done any laundry during the entire trip either. You can imagine the mountain, which is slowly getting smaller. First, I tackled the stockings: there were about fifty pairs. I washed and mended them—some had holes the size of a fist! They were reduced to forty pairs. I've finished them now, thank goodness, along with the handkerchiefs and underwear. Tomorrow it's the coloured clothes' turn. In two weeks, I hope to have finished the pile. After that, I'll have to do laundry every week because I don't have enough containers for so much. (Brunswig de Bamberg 46–47)

Her friendship with landowners Max Wlotzel (Uncle Max) and Lucas Bridges, and a visit to the grim home of a poor family of *gauchos*, offer Ella the opportunity to portray the social extremes of Patagonia. She moves with ease among the land, but wishes to keep her family culturally untouched. Her daughter María, the editor, is still surprised to read a letter from her mother in 1926, three and a half years after her arrival, in which she forbids their children from learning and speaking Spanish, forcing them to use only German. Although Ella writes that she's striving to improve her Spanish and interact with the local people, she fears her kids will lose their German identity. In that letter, Ella complains about her two-year-old son: "During my four-day absence, Hermancito learned so much Spanish that I became alarmed. I'm very angry and I'm constantly trying to correct him, so he'll go back to German. We don't give any importance to Castilian" (225). María replies to that view of her mother almost seventy years later, with a commentary that reflects on the self-image and the project that their parents had in mind about their stay in Argentina:

My mother's observation has given me much to think about. It's true that our parents had raised us to live in Germany, to such an extent that when we arrived in Berlin in 1929 and our schoolmates asked us to speak some Spanish, we could barely give them any examples. Although my parents never said so explicitly, they hadn't come with the intention of

staying in Argentina but rather planned to return to spend a comfortable old age in their homeland. This attitude, very common among foreigners who arrived in Argentina—I don't say "immigrants", because they specifically didn't want to be—persisted until the end of World War II. The newcomers got used to living in the new country and even came to love it, but they didn't interact with its inhabitants or take an interest in its culture and institutions. Identification with the new land only occurred with their children's generation. (Brunswig de Bamberg 225–26)

Thus, the family remained sheltered in the German cultural bubble during their early Patagonian years, and Ella refused to let her children assimilate any Spanish influence. Today, we hear a recurring message in Europe accusing people of other cultures, such as Muslims or Africans, for supposedly not wanting to accept their host country: "Immigrants don't want to integrate", some say. The case of Ella, German immigrant in Patagonia, may demonstrate that remaining confined within one's own community under protective measures is a social phenomenon caused not by a particular origin, but by the human need to feel at home.

At the same time, curiously, in a letter to her stepfather, "Dear Papa Sydow", on 10 November 1927, from the new home in Estancia Chacayal, Ella affirms that they already feel in the family "gladly Patagonian", considering that "only there is the original character of this beautiful country maintained", alluding to Argentina. She expresses great appreciation for the language and culture of the Patagonian natives, the Tehuelches, who, she regrets, have been decimated. She adds: "And what I find even worse is that the indigenous people are ashamed of their identity. Their language is despised, even though it's a beautiful language, rich in vowels, very different from Spanish, almost resembling German in its intonation. It's a great shame" (Brunswig de Bamberg 257).

In September 1929, Ella and the children returned temporarily to Germany while the father remained at the farm. The editor, María, takes on the lead voice in the final chapter, "Awakening", by including a text that she wrote in Germany in 1934 when she was 18 years old, describing the return trip from Patagonia and the departure of the ship *Monte Olivia* from Buenos Aires; the girl recalled the pain she suffered when she saw his father at the dock weaving goodbye:

I look down at where Dad is standing, waving his handkerchief incessantly, and suddenly my gaze fixes on him, my smile freezes, something rises from the depths of my throat and eyes: "There lies the last of the old land, now it's all over, now I'll never see Dad again, now...". And my head falls over the railing, sobs choke me, and I cry like I've never cried before. (Brunswig de Bamberg 307–08)

In the "Epilogue" added in the second edition, the editor-writer gives information about what happened with each member of the family after the Patagonian years described before. Her parents moved to Buenos Aires and died there: Hermann (who never came back to Germany) in 1971 and Ella in 1990. María says at the end of the book: "The two rest in a land where they had not thought of dying, but which became their second homeland." (316). For their children, it was perhaps their first.

German Migrants to Argentina

Argentine governments promoted immigration from Europe, and Hermann, Ella and their children were part of the flow of German-speaking migrants who chose the South

American country as their new home. The first German settlers arrived in 1825, as the Embassy in Buenos Aires noted on its website during the commemoration of the bicentenary of the landmark in 2025 (“200 años”). That exodus, which has resulted in around 3.5 million Argentines with German-speaking ancestors, was socially diverse and included working-class people, major entrepreneurs, middle- and upper-class families such as Ella’s, political activists, artists, scientists, exiles, and refugees, including Jews persecuted under Nazism before World War II, as well as former Nazi members after their defeat.

Sometimes the Western public opinion is surprised when they see immigrants arriving from Syria, Morocco, Senegal, or Turkey, which are actually neighbours of Europe, very close to the continent. And yet we now see, if we look at the map, that the distances they travelled a century ago from Germany to Argentina, for example, were ten times greater. Therefore, the concept of distance and proximity is very relative.

Let’s mirror some characteristics of this flux, particularly in the first decades of the twentieth century, by picking three examples of documents of German travellers and ships. They are on display at the Museum of Immigration, managed by the Universidad Tres de Febrero of Buenos Aires, associated with the research project Trans.Arch. These documents provide information about what it was like to travel in the epoch when the Brunswig family arrived. For example, the registration card of “Einstein, Doctor Albert”, the genius from Berlin, who disembarks on March 25, 1925, after crossing the world from Hamburg onboard the *Cap Polonio*, in first class. The official record of the General Directorate of Immigration states that he’s a 45-year-old professor who speaks German, Spanish and French, is in “Good health” and has “no defects”. He comes for the first time to Argentina; the reason? “Visitarse” (touring).

Fig. 9, 10 and 11. Documents shown in the Museo de la Inmigración, in the former Hotel de Inmigrantes in Buenos Aires: the arrival record of the German scientist Albert Einstein, a list of German travellers from Bremen and the ticket of a Spanish girl who came to Argentina on a German vessel.

The list of second-class passengers on the *Coburg*, operating on the Bremen-Buenos Aires line of Norddeutsche Lloyd, the Bremen-based company, dated 24 December (with no year mentioned, presumably in the 1920s), indicates what the passenger manifest of the ship on which the Brunswig family migrated might have looked like. The majority were men, mostly young.

It’s difficult to calculate today’s equivalence of the cost of their tickets, because the German Mark was very volatile at that time, in a period of hyperinflation. But there’s another document that can help in an indirect way. In October 1925, a 16 year old Spanish girl boarded in La Coruña a German ship of Norddeutsche Lloyd going from Bremen to Buenos Aires. She paid 580 pesetas for her third-class ticket, plus 7.75 pesetas in taxes. That would be equivalent to at least 1,550 euros today, according to a specialized calculator.²

So it means that today a return flight ticket would cost the equivalent of a three- or two-week third-class ship passage from Germany to Buenos Aires with a stopover in Spain. That implies how much the Brunswig had to pay to travel to Patagonia to reunite the father: five one-way-only tickets (two adults, the mother and the cook, and three children) which will now cost around 7,500 euros.

² <https://www.measuringworth.com/calculators/spaincompare/relativevalue-es.php>.

It is easy to imagine the Brunswig, or another family like theirs, discussing “What are we going to do with our lives?” and then deciding, “Let’s go to Patagonia, we have an opportunity there”. They then threw themselves completely into the unknown. We can glimpse their first impressions of Argentina by looking at the historical photographs preserved at the Museo del Hotel de Inmigrantes. After a month at sea, they would arrive from Germany at this massive shelter, designed for those who could not afford to stay in private hotels. The images show people aboard the ships, their landing, piles of luggage ready for a new life; beds in vast collective dormitories; and huge dining halls for the newly arrived, who could sleep and eat here for up to five days. In their traditional clothing, we can recognize their cultural differences. Soon afterward, they would create and join their associations, schools, churches, and clubs organized along national, social, cultural, religious, political or linguistic boundaries, in order to preserve their identity and seek protection within their community and shared culture. Most would also learn Spanish and incorporate an Argentine dimension into their idiosyncrasy, while at the same time attempting to maintain ties with the family left behind in their homeland. Today, migrants remain permanently connected through social media and mobile phones. In 1919, by contrast, one would leave, and years might pass before families were reunited. Only letters, such as Ella’s, kept them connected.

Ella Hoffmann and her family “colonize” a territory, implanting their own culture and identity; yet, from the distance of time and space, her daughter María Bamberg reconstructs the history of her German family “as a contribution to the history of Argentina”, as Gutiérrez Koester points out (“Cartas” 286; my trans.). *Allá en la Patagonia* might initially have interested only the author’s family or the German-Argentine community. However, thanks to its literary quality and historical significance, it engages the reader and ultimately serves as a mirror not only of the history and nature of this American region, but also of the lives of millions of people who migrated to Argentina from all over the world. Furthermore, the woman on the red cover of the book that I found on Corrientes Avenue represents the universal archetype of the foreigner abroad. National and personal particularities change, but a shared humanity remains, allowing us to identify with the protagonists, with others, regardless of differences in language or origin. I recall the day before the celebration honouring Roland Spiller, when my son Eduardo and I, while strolling through Wiesbaden, saw in the park opposite the train station a gathering for refugee children. And I realize that this story never ends.

More Voices, Old and New

Within German culture in Argentina, the voice of Ella Hoffmann de Brunswig, brought to attention through the editorial work of her daughter, was exceptional but not unique. At least two other German women travellers in Patagonia who were contemporaries of Ella wrote and published their visions of this land: Bertha Koessler-Ilg (1881–1965) and Christel (Wallich de) Koerte (1916–1958, or possibly 1956). Regula Rohland de Langbehn, founder and director of the Centre for Documentation of German-Speaking Immigration in Argentina (DIHA), highlighted this connection when she published, in 2017, an edition bringing together writings by the three authors. The works of María Brunswig de Bamberg, together with the memoirs of her sister Irene Brunswig de Neddermann (*A caballo por la vida*, 2006), extend the corpus of German-Argentinian female narratives on Patagonia. All of these works belong to the broader field of German women travel writing between Germany, Spain, and Hispanic America, examined in the volume edited by Gutiérrez Koester and García-Wistädt (*Viajeras*). For earlier

predecessors in Patagonian literature from the period 1870–1914, predominantly male authors, see the study of travel narratives, chronicles, memoirs, and other writings by Grupo de Investigación de la Universidad del Comahue.

The need to build history with stories continues today through new initiatives that follow the same memorial path traced by María Bamberg. The digital edition of the long-established newspaper *Argentinisches Tageblatt* regularly publishes feature articles on the adventurous lives of German ancestors. The German Embassy offers another illustrative example. In 2025, it commemorated the two hundredth anniversary of the first settlement of compatriots in Argentina, and one of the activities announced on its website, alongside the creation of online virtual visits to museums belonging to German communities (Embajada “Recorridos”), was a call for individuals to share their family histories via email. “Do you have stories, photos, or documents to share? We want to hear from you! Your contribution helps preserve collective memory. Contact us at: contacto@200alemaniaenargentina.ar” (Embajada *200 años*). It will be fascinating to read, listen to, and view these contributions. Countless untold experiences are still seeking their writers, editors, and readers.

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